

CONTINUOUS LINKAGES AND ENGAGEMENT TOWARD QUALITY EDUCATIONAL SERVICES: BASIS FOR MANAGEMENT FRAMEWORK

JULIE ANN V. CERVANA¹

DELON A. CHING²

julie.cervana@deped.gov.ph¹

delon.ching@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0003-4241-9013¹

0000-0003-1435-4371²

Ambray Elementary School, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

Continuous linkages and engagement toward quality educational service are the basis for the management framework of the school. Elements of continuous linkage and school and community engagement as perceived by the teacher respondents. To support this study, it tackled the school and community continuous linkages and engagement in the educational system and it focused on the quality educational services provided. A descriptive and correlational study type of research was used to describe the relationship of the school and community continuous linkages and engagement toward quality of educational service provided in public elementary schools with 149 teacher respondents in 10 elementary schools in Ambray District, Division of San Pablo City in the academic year 2020- 2021 and the research instrument used for gathering data in the study are self-made survey questionnaire with some concepts adapted and modified. The level of performance of the teacher in terms of content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment and diversity of learners, curriculum and planning, and assessment and reporting are all “excellent”. The level of performance of teachers in public elementary schools is significantly affected by the element’s continuous linkage between school and community engagement. The level of performance of the school is significantly affected by the elements of continuous linkage between school and community engagement. The study suggests that the teachers may include the elements of continuous linkage that will help to have quality educational service. They may ask the help of stakeholders to participate in the school programs and projects.

Keywords: Continuous Linkages, Engagement, Quality Educational Services, Management Framework